

Price Bubble Detection In The Covid-19 Period: Empirical Evidence From BIST Bank Index ¹

Diler TÜRKOĞLU² Fatih KONAK³

Article Type / Makale Türü: Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi

Vol / Cilt 7 (Issue/Sayı 2) 2025: 142-153

 10.5281/zenodo.18107176

Cite as / Atıf: Türkoğlu, D., Konak, F. (2025). Price Bubble Detection In The Covid-19 Period: Empirical Evidence From BIST Bank Index, Quantrade Journal of Complex Systems in Social Sciences, 7 (2), 142-153.

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18107176

Received/ Gönderilme: 13.11.2025

Revision / Revizyon: 11.12.2025

Accepted / Kabul: 18.12.2025

Abstract

Price bubbles are known to upset market equilibrium and affect investor choices in times of financial crisis. Determining which assets are impacted by price bubbles is therefore crucial for scholars and market players alike. Accordingly, this study investigates whether price bubbles developed in the shares of banks that are part of the BIST Banking Index between March 11, 2020, when the Covid-19 pandemic initially surfaced in Turkey, and April 9, 2022, when all pandemic-related restrictions were repealed. The study also looked into whether these bubbles varied amongst banks. To find price bubbles, the SADF and GSADF tests were used. Price bubbles have developed in the shares of Akbank, Halkbank, and Şekerbank, according to the findings of the analysis carried out at a 5% significance level. In contrast, the shares of ICBC, Garanti Bankası, and Vakıfbank did not exhibit any price bubbles. Test results from other banks were not included in the analysis because they did not fit the requirements for statistical significance.

Key Words: Price Bubbles, GSADF, BIST Bank Index.

Covid-19 Sürecinde Fiyat Balonlarının Tespiti: BİST BANKA Endeksi Uygulaması

Öz

Finansal krizler sırasında fiyat balonlarının piyasa dengesini bozduğu ve yatırımcı kararlarını etkilediği bilinmektedir. Bu nedenle, fiyat balonlarının hangi varlıklar üzerinde oluştuğunu belirlemek hem piyasa katılımcıları hem de araştırmacılar için önem taşımaktadır. Bu doğrultuda yapılan bu çalışmada, Türkiye’de Covid-19 salgınının ilk görüldüğü 11 Mart 2020 tarihinden, salgına yönelik tedbirlerin tamamen kaldırıldığı 9 Nisan 2022 tarihine kadar geçen süreçte, BİST Banka Endeksi’ne dahil bankaların hisse senetlerinde fiyat balonlarının oluşup oluşmadığı incelenmiştir. Ayrıca, bu balonların bankalar arasında farklılık gösterip göstermediği de araştırılmıştır. Çalışmada fiyat balonlarının tespiti için SADF ve GSADF testleri uygulanmıştır. %5 anlamlılık düzeyinde yapılan analizler sonucunda, Akbank, Halkbank ve Şekerbank hisselerinde fiyat balonu oluştuğu tespit edilmiştir. Buna karşılık, Vakıfbank, Garanti Bankası ve ICBC hisselerinde fiyat balonuna rastlanmamıştır. Diğer bankalar için yapılan testlerde elde edilen bulgular, istatistiksel anlamlılık kriterlerini karşılamadığı için değerlendirme dışında bırakılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Fiyat Balonu, GSADF, BİST Banka Endeksi.

¹ This article is an extended and final version of the abstract presented by the authors at the 22nd International Business Congress organized by Nişantaşı University in Istanbul on September 7-9, 2023. Quantrade tarafından yayınlanmıştır. Bu makale Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) lisansı altında yayınlanmıştır / Published by Quantrade. This article is published under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) licence.

² Ardahan University, Türkiye, dilerturkoglu@ardahan.edu.tr, 0000-0001-5247-1590

³ Hitit University, Türkiye, fatihkonak@hitit.edu.tr, 0000-0002-6917-5082

Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19, which was named as a new type of coronavirus by the WHO, as a pandemic, and the implementation of measures worldwide caused the economy to be negatively affected. The pandemic has shown its detrimental effects on foreign trade, tourism, agriculture, and various sectors with the implementation of measures (Ogunnusi et al., 2020; Temir, 2020; Torun Kayabaşı, 2020; Türkoğlu, 2021; Marcu, 2021; Ulusoy, 2020).

Consequently, volatilities that arise on pricing apart from the current influencing elements; alternatively put, beginning with the ideal risk sharing, a slight departure from one component may incite a deviation from another. In all stable equilibria, asset price distortions may arise, and optimum risk sharing will not be stable. Financial bubbles arise from the self-reinforcing belief that an asset's price is determined by one or more variables that are either genuinely relevant-that is, by parameters not included in market Fundamentals-or by essentially irrelevant variables (Diba and Grossman, 1988:520).

Stated differently, ongoing and systematic price disparities between the virtual and actual values of investment instruments are what are known as financial bubbles (Anavatan and Kayacan, 2018:125). Bubbles are characterized by sharp gains in asset prices that are followed by a collapse. When the price is higher than the asset's worth, a bubble develops. This could happen when investors cling onto an asset thinking they can sell it for more than some other investors, even though the asset's price is more than its true intrinsic value (Brunnermeier, 2016:28).

The formation of bubbles in the prices of securities and other investment instruments leads to a rise in demand for these products; nevertheless, abrupt decreases and significant losses follow the deflation of the bubble. The market is out of equilibrium as a result of all these swings (Çakar, 2022:107). Therefore, financial bubble prediction and analysis are crucial due to the influence bubbles have on financial markets and their strong correlation with a potential financial disaster. Asset bubbles occur in three distinct stages. The growth in loans is matched by an increase in the value of assets like stocks and real estate during the first phase of financial liberalization. As the bubble expands, prices will continue to rise. In the second stage, the bubble bursts, and asset values collapse, sometimes over a longer period but frequently in a matter of days or months. Lastly, the default of several businesses and other entities that took out loans to purchase assets at exorbitant rates characterizes the third stage. There are currency and banking problems after this wave of defaults. The real sector of the economy can frequently experience long-lasting issues as a result of defaults, financial crises, and currency issues (Allen and Gale, 2000:236). The proper operation of financial markets depends on the analysis of speculative bubbles in banking indexes. These bubbles can have a direct effect on the banking industry's risk management and valuation as assets that appreciate too much might cause serious financial instability after collapses. Banks can make better investment decisions and avoid possible losses by spotting speculative bubbles early on. Additionally, these assessments allow policymakers and regulators to oversee markets with greater knowledge and efficacy. By analyzing each company separately and determining whether there is a differentiation between companies, this research seeks to identify the price bubbles that occurred in 10 banks quoted in the BIST Bank Index between March 11, 2020-the date the Covid-19 case was first detected in Turkey-and April 9, 2022-the date when Covid-19 measures were completely abolished (Numbered 318004 published in the Official Newspaper). The purpose of the SADF (Sup Augmented Dickey-Fuller) and GSDAF (Generalized Sup Augmented Dickey-Fuller) tests, which were carried out during the empirical application period, is to inform investors and decision-makers regarding the potential impact of financial bubbles on the market and the likelihood of a crisis.

This research focuses on price bubbles specific to banks in Turkey during the Covid-19 period, as it examines heterogeneous bubble behavior among banks and provides sector-specific information for risk management. Following the examination of the literature, the research's methodology, data set, and analysis results are discussed and assessed.

1. Literature Review

Below are some instances of empirical applications from national and international literature that are relevant to the subject. To ascertain the return volatility and price bubbles of the gold price, TL/US Dollar, TL/Euro, and deposit interest rate on the BIST 100 Index for the years 2022–2016, Korkmaz et al. (2016) employed the TGARCH and GSADF tests. The empirical results demonstrate that although gold price bubbles reduce the volatility of the BIST 100 Index, rises in gold and dollar exchange rates enhance the volatility of the index.

Çağlı and Mandacı (2017) used data from 21 indexes under the BIST framework to test for the presence of rational speculative bubbles in the market employing the dividend yield ratio between 2006 and 2016. The examination produced proof of the presence of speculative bubbles in the stock market as well as in other industries. In a similar vein, Kılıç (2020) conducted the GSADF experiment with monthly index closing prices between 1994 and 2020 to examine the possibility of price bubbles in the stock markets of the BRICS-T countries. The findings of the research indicated that price bubbles existed in the Chinese stock market, but no proof of price bubbles in other countries' stock markets was discovered. In their research to determine whether there are several bubbles and related particular events in various industrial sectors of the Pakistan Stock Exchange, Liaquat, Nazir and Ahmad (2019) employed the GSADF test. Many bubbles are present in the KSE-100 Index, depending to the assessment. Li et al. (2020) figure out the start and end points of prospective speculative bubbles by examining natural gas prices in the USA, EU, and Asia. Two bubble events occurred in the EU, six in Asia, and five in the US throughout the research period, according to the findings. It was discovered that the EU bubbles lasted longer. Chang et al., (2021) applied generalized SADF (GSADF) tests for the identical purpose in their analysis, which sought to determine whether there was a bubble in US markets during the COVID-19 period. There are bubbles in the US stock market during sub-sample periods, according to the research's conclusions, which are based on daily Dow Jones stock price indexes. Taking a different angle, Li et al. (2021) endeavored to ascertain if medical mask costs in China experienced a bubble during the COVID-19 period. Three stock prices exhibited several bubbles, but no bubbles in the stock market as a whole, according to the GSADF test findings applied to the Shanghai Composite Index (SHCI) and Shenzhen Component Index (SZCI).

Çakar (2022) applied the GSADF approach to examine the price bubble creation in conventional and participation indices during the COVID-19 timeframe. The results of the examination suggested that there were seven price bubbles in the XU100 Index, six in the XUMAL Index, and seven in the XUHIZ Index bubble assessments. Four price bubbles were found in the KATL Index, five in the KAT50 Index, and six in the KATMP Index, according to the bubble analysis derived from participation indices. From a comparable perspective, Wang et al. (2022a) evaluated the bubbles in the tourism stock markets of China and Taiwan during the Covid-19 epidemic using both the generalized and augmented Dickey-Fuller (SADF) tests. For Taiwan, they employed the weekly stock price index from 4 January 2000 to 27 April 2020, while for China, they used the index from 13 August 2007 to 27 April 2020. The findings demonstrate that there were bubbles in Taiwan's stock market for travel during a few subsample times, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Kartal (2022) employed the GSADF and BSADF techniques to analyze the housing market bubbles that occurred in Turkey and the TR71 Region between 2010 and 2021. As a consequence of the study, bubbles were found using both methodologies throughout Turkey and the TR71 Region. Furthermore, Wang and Kim (2022) assess the probability of price bubble transfer in addition to examining whether it may occur between the gas and oil markets. The study's conclusions suggest that price bubbles in the oil sector may spill over into the gas market as the GSADF data for gas prices Granger-cause the GSADF numbers for oil prices.

Demmler and Fernández Domínguez (2022) examined daily data from 2013 to 2019 to identify Bitcoin price bubbles. Numerous speculative bubble trends in Bitcoin prices were discovered. The speculation that drove these trends peaked at the end of 2017. The presence and timing of price bubbles in NFT and DeFi

markets, Wang et al. (2022b) employed the SADF and GSADF tests. According to their analysis, speculative bubbles are present in both the NFT and DeFi markets; NFT bubbles are more frequent and have a larger average explosive magnitude than DeFi bubbles. The goal of Fendi et al. (2023) is to figure out if the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) has logical speculative bubbles throughout two sample periods: 2010–2018 and 2004–2009. For the first sample period, ASE returns show signs of a reasonable speculative bubble, according to the study. In addition, Lehnert (2023) analyzes price-dividend ratios from S&P 500 stock market data to identify past speculative bubbles. An explosive movement that may be connected to the new "green technology" has been identified as a consequence of the GSADF testing, particularly starting in June 2021. Also et al. (2023) used the SADF and GSADF techniques to analyze monthly All Share Index data from 1985 until 2021 to analyze various bubble eras. Consequently, over the relevant era, many bubbles were identified in the Indian stock market (NSE).

Li et al (2021) the introduction of Bitcoin, which is seen as a turning event, marked the beginning of the cryptocurrency age. There have been notable price swings and quick price gains since Bitcoin's inception. Examining the speculative bubbles in the Bitcoin market is the goal of this essay. This study analyzed the existence of bubbles in the Bitcoin market using the GSADF test, estimated the emergence and collapse times of bubbles, looked into the causes of bubbles based on chronology, and offered some policy recommendations using Bitstamp's daily closing price data from September 13, 2011, to October 12, 2020. The following are the conclusions drawn from this investigation: (1) A lot of speculative bubbles exist. Four long and four short bubbles were found. (2) The occurrence of pertinent events and policies is typically linked to the formation and bust of bubbles. (3) The market for Bitcoin is still developing. One major policy risk that leads to speculative activity is policy pronouncements. The use of the newly created bubble detecting technique GSADF in the Bitcoin market is a significant novelty of this research. This technique can identify the presence and length of several Bitcoin bubbles. Acharya (2024) unpredictable price gains followed by subsequent decreases are the hallmark of stock bubbles, which cause investors to suffer large losses. This study investigates the capacity to identify unit roots, statistical stationarity, and numerous structural fractures using real-time monitoring data. The GSADF test shows greater accuracy and efficacy in detecting stock bubbles and regularly performs better than the SADF test in rejecting the null hypothesis.

Li et al. (2025) interest in price volatility and the ensuing price bubble phenomena has grown due to the crucial role commodities assets play in economic growth. This study employed the GSADF approach to identify explosive occurrences in four commodities markets: cotton, soybeans, copper, and crude oil. The variables driving these boom-bust occurrences were also investigated using a rare events logit model. The four commodities markets had many price bubbles between January 1980 and July 2022, according to empirical findings. Copper has the biggest market bubble risk, followed by soybeans, cotton, and crude oil. The exuberance and collapse of bubble behavior were linked to microeconomic causes and geopolitical developments, according to research on the components that cause bubbles. Specifically, the chance of price bubbles emerging is greatly increased by global economic development and the devaluation of the dollar. Price bubbles are significantly impacted by geopolitical risk, and it has been discovered that particular geopolitical acts (GPA) rather than geopolitical threats (GPT) are more likely to cause bubbles to spread. The characteristics and evolution of commodity market bubbles were clarified in the research, and practical guidance for investors and regulators on price control and investment decisions was provided. Guo et al. (2025) The paper examines asset bubbles in the NFT and cryptocurrency markets and evaluates how market sentiment and cryptocurrency prices affect the development of NFT bubbles. The Generalized Unit Root Test (GSADF test) is used in the NFT market to analyze price bubbles on seven main cryptocurrencies, as well as related projects and submarkets. Three distinct cryptocurrency booms were identified in the study, and a deflationary period in 2022 was observed. In terms of bubble dynamics, a significant positive correlation has been found between NFTs and the majority of cryptocurrencies. Crucially, different market sentiment indicators have varied effects on NFT bubbles; the GEPU index and Google Trends data exhibit negative effects, whilst the VIX index has a positive influence.

Candelon and Boninsegna (2024) "Which strategies help identify stock market bubbles, and to what extent do these phenomena affect overall market stability and the performance of investment portfolios?" is the research topic that drives this article. This goal was accomplished via a variety of techniques. First, a variety of bubble identification methods, including structural break tests and GSADF, were used in relation to the original goal. Variations in return distributions, fundamental values, and deviations from historical patterns were also examined. Specific firms, such as Microsoft, were considered, and the dot-com bubble was treated as a real-world case study. Attention was given to how the results of several tests could be integrated and how such integration might support the identification of speculative bubbles.

2. Dataset and Methodology

Examining speculative bubbles in banking indices is crucial, especially when it comes to the financial stability and portfolio management of banks. Because of the abrupt falls that accompany unsustainable price gains, these bubbles can make it more difficult for banks to assess credit and manage liquidity. The banking industry may lower possible credit risks and get ready for future financial shocks by effectively detecting market bubbles. Furthermore, banks can create more cautious rules against such swings since market psychology frequently shapes speculative bubbles. These assessments contribute to the development of a safer investing environment for investors and assist financial authorities in better monitoring the industry. The goal of the study is to pinpoint potential price bubbles in banks that were listed in the BIST Bank (XBANK) Index between March 11, 2020, the day Turkey experienced its first instance of COVID-19, and April 9, 2022, the day all restrictions were removed. As a consequence, Table 1 lists the banks that participated in the index trade and were examined along with their BIST codes. Also, it should be underlined that the Datastream database is the source of the data. The stages of the event study methodology are as follows:

Table 1: Banks Listed in The BIST Bank Index and Included in the Analysis

Company Title	Code
Akbank A.Ş.	AKBNK
Albaraka Türk Katılım A.Ş.	ALBRK
Icbc Türkiye Bankası A.Ş.	ICBCT
Şekerbank A.Ş.	SKBNK
Türkiye Garanti Bank A.Ş.	GARAN
Türkiye Halk Bankası A.Ş.	ISCTR
Türkiye Sınai Kalkınma Bankası A.Ş.	TSKB
Türkiye Vakıflar Bankası T.A.O.	VAKBN
Yapı ve Kredi Bankası A.Ş.	YKBNK
İş Bankası	ISCTR

3. SADF and GSADF Model

It is a right-tailed, recursive unit root test designed to identify the presence and timing of speculative bubbles. It is based on the SADF model put out by Phillips et al. (2015). T is a straightforward extension of the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, a unit root test, to a multiple bubble setting in a time series context. That being said, this process is distinguished by four main elements. First, since recursive estimating performs well, this approach is predicated on the notion of continually performing the ADF test on subsamples of the data in an iterative fashion rather than on the entire sample. The question test is renowned for its capacity for efficient information utilization (Cheunga et al., 2015:2353; Çağlı and Mandacı, 2017:66). The SADF Model is formulated as follows;

$$\sup_{r \in \{r_0, 1\}} ADF_r \rightarrow \sup_{r \in \{r_0, 1\}} \frac{\int_0^r \tilde{w} dW}{\left(\int_0^r \tilde{W}^2\right)^{1/2}} \quad (1)$$

It is discovered that the SADF test is insufficient for identifying bubbles in empirical studies with abrupt changes and long-run series. This is a result of the SADF test's limited capacity to identify individual bubbles. As a result, the SADF test is inconclusive if there are several bubbles in the data used for the study. Stated differently, it is found that the statistical performance of the SADF test is insufficient when there are several asset bubbles, non-linear series, or structural fractures. (Phillips et al., 2015; Çakar, 2022:111).

The generalized SADF test (GSADF) was devised by Phillips et al. (2015) in response to these findings. The GSADF test is constructed using the recursively flexible estimate windows and the regression equation that yields the results of the ADF test. By considering the non-linear structures and structural breaks found during the analysis of time series over the long term, this approach (the GSADF test) yields more consistent and accurate results in situations when many speculative price bubbles may arise in the same timeframe (Çağlı and Mandacı, 2017:66).

Unlike the SADF method, the GSADF changes not only the first observation of the sub-sample (r_1) but also the extreme point (r_2). Phillips et al (2015) define the GSADF statistic as the largest ADF statistic in this double curve across all feasible ranges of r_1 and r_2 .

The GSADF statistic is defined as the largest ADF statistic in this double recursion over the entire feasible ranges of r_1 and r_2 and is denoted by GSADF(r_0) (Phillips, et al., 2015:1049; Sharma and Escobari, 2018:422).

$$GSADF(r_0) = \sup_{\substack{r_2 \in [r_0, 1] \\ r_1 \in [0, r_2 - r_1]}} \{ADF_{r_1}^{r_2}\} \quad (2)$$

In line with this theoretical background, the hypotheses formulated to determine whether price bubbles occurred in the banks listed in the BIST Bank Index and included in the analysis during the Covid-19 period are as follows;

H₀ = No price bubble occurred in the BIST Bank Index and companies during the Covid-19 period ($p > 0.05$).

H₁ = There was a price bubble in the BIST Bank Index and companies during the Covid-19 period ($p < 0.05$).

If statistically significant findings are detected as a result of the analyses, hypothesis H₀ will be rejected and hypothesis H₁ will be accepted.

4. Analysis and Findings

The objectives of this research are to spot price bubbles in Turkish banks that are part of the BIST Bank Index between March 11, 2020, and April 9, 2022, and to monitor how these banks' financial performances differ from one another. The SADF and GSADF techniques were used to analyze the price data of the BIST Bank Index as well as the shares of the ten banks that were part of the analysis separately. Table 2 displays the analysis's GSADF results.

Table 2: GSADF Test Results For BIST Bank Index and Banks

Index/Banks	Test Stat.	P- Value
BIST Bank	2.337558	0.020**
Akbank	2.27780	0.020**
ICBC	1.936088	0.140
Halkbank	2.173814	0.030**
İşbank	3.915007	0.000***

Yapı kredi	3.375713	0.000***
Albaraka	2.024987	0.080
Şekerbank	2.892912	0.020**
Türkiye Sınai Kalkınma Bankası	12.59253	0.000***
Vakıfbank	1.787376	0.230
Garanti	1.780926	0.230

At the 5% and 1% levels, respectively, ** and *** indicate statistical significance. The critical values were determined to be 1% (2.909251), 5% (2.147975), and 10% (1.994348). The Monte-Carlo simulation with 100 replications yields critical results, and the initial Windows size is 0.10.

The formation of price bubbles in the Covid-19 process is graphically represented in Graph 1. The 95% critical value sequence is marked by the red line in the graphs, while the reverse SADF sequence is represented by the blue line. The beginning of the price bubble can be observed by the locations where the blue line crosses the red line; the deflation of the price bubble is indicated by the points where it crosses the red line in the opposite direction.

Graph 1. GSADF Test Graphs of BIST Bank Index and Banks

Graph 1(a). Garanti GSADF testi grafiği

Graph 1(b). Akbank GSADF testi grafiği

Graph 1(c). ICBC GSADF testi grafiği

Graph 1(d). Halkbank GSADF testi grafiği

Graph 1(e). İşbank GSADF testi grafiği

Graph 1(f). Yapıkredi GSADF testi grafiği

Graph 1(g). Albaraka Bank GSADF Test Graph

Graph 1(h). Şekerbank GSADF Test Graph

Graph 1(i). Sınai Kalkınma Bank GSADF Test

Graph 1(i). Vakıfbank GSADF Test Graph

Graph 1(j). BIST Bank Index GSADF Test Graph

It is possible to conclude from the analysis of the charts that a bubble commenced to form in the BIST Bank Index during the third quarter of 2020. The fourth quarter of 2020 marked the reemergence of the bubble that had burst in the previous quarter. In just one quarter, many bubbles burst and deflated. The bubble that started to form after the first quarter of 2021 persisted until the start of the second quarter, during which time it began to collapse.

Two further bubbles transpired in the final quarter of 2021, after these. In 2022, the effects of the bubbles that burst in the same quarter disappeared. Thus, during the COVID-19 era, the BIST Bank Index may reference up to five bubbles in total. Analysis of the data in Table 2 demonstrates significant results at the 5% significance level. Analyses done at Akbank, Halkbank, and Şekerbank similarly indicated significance at the 5% level of significance.

Following an analysis of these banks' graphs, seven balloons were found in Akbank, three in Halk Bank, and nine in Şekerbank. There have been periodic price bubbles: one in the third quarter of 2020, two in the fourth quarter of 2020, one in the first quarter of 2021, two in the fourth quarter of 2021, and one in the first quarter of 2022. One price bubble was found in the second quarter of 2020 and one in the first quarter of 2022 when analysis focused on Halkbank.

Ultimately, six price bubbles were found in Şekerbank during the second quarter of 2020, and one in the fourth. The same bank had one price bubble in the first quarter of 2021 and another in the fourth quarter of 2021. Thus, between the pertinent periods, it may be concluded that Halkbank is less susceptible than other companies. These results show that price bubbles for the BIST Bank Index and the banks under analysis appeared both constantly and during certain times. The market's volatility and the rapid burst and deflation of bubbles are highlighted, especially between the third quarter of 2020 and the first quarter of 2021. The uncertainties and economic instability brought about by COVID-19 are reflected in this circumstance. The analysis of bubbles at Akbank, Halkbank, and Şekerbank shows that they affect bank price fluctuations in varied ways, but certain banks (like Halkbank) have less bubbles than others. This might suggest that these banks have a more robust approach to risk management or a structure that is more adaptable to changes in the market. In addition, investors must exercise caution and diversify their holdings to guard against these price bubbles. Price bubbles, in particular, can have an impact on banks' risk assessments and investment choices during specific times. The success of certain tactics and internal control systems is demonstrated by the fact that some banks, like Halkbank, encounter fewer bubbles than others. These analysis will be very helpful in forecasting future financial market bubbles and influencing investment choices.

5. Conclusion

It is clear that price bubbles upset the equilibrium in price creation and are a major factor in financial crises. An economic catastrophe is probably going to arise from these price-based bubbles that have moved from the real to the financial sectors. The assets that are impacted by price bubbles and the duration of their duration are therefore crucial. Price bubbles are a major contributor to financial crises and obviously upset the balance in price creation. These price-based bubbles have the potential to expand from the real sector to the financial sector, which would be disastrous for the economy. As a result, the assets impacted by price bubbles and how long these bubbles last are crucial. Such bubbles can result in overvaluation, which can harm both market players and the stability of the economy as a whole. In particular, these bubbles can result in large financial losses if the timing of their rupture and the length of their influence on the market are not accurately understood. These market swings have the potential to erode investor confidence, jeopardize market liquidity, and exacerbate macroeconomic instability. This motivation led to the study's objective of identifying price bubbles in banks that were part of the BIST Bank Index. The SADF and GSADF methods were employed to analyze the price data of the BIST Bank Index as well as the shares of each of the ten banks that were part of the analysis separately. Apart from identifying price bubbles in banks, the objective of these analyses is to highlight the distinctions among the concerned companies.

In this context, statistically significant results indicating the occurrence of a price bubble in the BIST Bank Index, Akbank, Halkbank, and Şekerbank were obtained from studies carried out at a 5% significance level. Consequently, the H₀ hypothesis is disproved. For the BIST Bank Index and banks, there are 5, 7, 3, and 9 price bubbles, respectively. These bubbles are seen to be transient in all three banks. Though bubbles were found in banks other than Vakıfbank, Garanti, and ICBC at different confidence intervals, they are not statistically significant since they fall outside of the 5% significance interval. Examining the research's graphs reveals that the bubbles that developed in the firms varied in length and frequency. As a consequence, variations from fair value, or only fair value, may be used to explain the bubble expansion that was seen within the parameters of the outcomes.

Therefore, the study's conclusions are consistent with those of Çağlı and Mandacı (2017) and Çakar (2022). The findings of the research are thought to be significant for scholars, investors, and market participants. It is due to the potential for a financial catastrophe to result from the exceptional price increase that occurred during the bubble period and the subsequent collapse. In light of this, it is crucial and might add to the body of knowledge to analyze price bubbles in various indexes at different times. Furthermore, it may be relevant in the process of investors strengthening their risk management methods by developing portfolios that are more resistant to speculative fluctuations.

Ethical Considerations of the Study

It is declared that the study was designed to realistically and ethically meet the needs, and that integrity was maintained in obtaining data, concluding the study, and publishing the results. Ethical committee approval was not required for this research. No research requiring ethics committee approval was conducted in this study.

Informed Consent

There was no need to obtain informed consent from individuals, as the study did not involve any procedures or interventions on human participants.

Author Contributions

Idea/Concept: D.T, F.K.; Design: D.T, F.K.; Supervision/Consultancy: D.T, F.K.; Resources: D.T, F.K.; Data Collection and/or Processing: D.T, F.K.; Analysis and/or Interpretation: D.T, F.K.; Literature Review: D.T, F.K.; Writing: D.T, F.K.; Critical Review: D.T, F.K.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflict of interest

Funding

The study did not receive any financial support from individuals or institutions.

Declarations

This article is an extended and final version of the abstract presented by the authors at the 22nd International Business Congress organized by Nişantaşı University in Istanbul on September 7-9, 2023.

References

- Acharya, D. (2024). Comparative Analysis Of Stock Bubble İn S&P 500 Individual Stocks: A Study Using SADF And GSADF Models. *Journal Of Risk And Financial Management*, 17(2), 59.
- Allen, Franklin And Gale, Douglas (2000), “*Bubbles And Crises*”, The Economic Journal, S.110(460), Ss.236-244.
- Anavatan, Aygöl And Kayacan, Yalçın (2018), “*Bıst 100 Endeksinde Balon Etkisinin İncelenmesi*”, Avrasya Sosyal Ve Ekonomi Araştırmaları Dergisi, S.5(8), Ss.124-131.
- Boninsegna, G., & Candelon, B. Analysis Of Stock Bubbles: Detection, Impact On Market Stability, And Portfolios’ Reactions.
- Brunnermeier, Markus (2016), “*Bubbles*”, Banking Crises: Perspectives From The New Palgrave Dictionary (Ed. Garrett Jones), Palgrave Macmillan Publisher, London (Uk), Ss.28-36.
- Chang, Tsangyao, Hsu, Chen-Min And Wang, Mei-Chih (2021), “*Bubbles During Covid-19 Period: Evidence From The United States Using The Generalized Sub Adf Test*”, *Holistica: Journal Of Business And Public Administration*, S.12(1), Ss.49-56.
- Cheunga, Adrian, Roca, Eduardo And Su, Jen-Je (2015), “*Crypto-Currency Bubbles: Anapplication Of The Phillips–Shi–Yu (2013) Methodology On Mt. Goxbitcoinprices*”, *Applied Economics*, S.47(23), Ss.2348-358.
- Çağlı, Efe Çağlar And Evrim Mandacı, Pınar (2017), “*Borsa İstanbul’da Rasyonel Balonvarlığı: Sektör Endeksleri Üzerine Biranaliz*”, *Finans Politik Ve Ekonomik Yorumlar*, S.6(29), Ss.63-76.
- Çakar, Recep (2022), “*Katılım Ve Konvansiyonel Endekslerin Fiyat Balonları Açısından Test Edilmesi: Kovid-19 Dönemi Türkiye’den Ampirik Kanıtlar*”, *International Journal Of Islamic Economics And Finance Studies*, S.8(1), Ss.106-122.
- Demmler, Michael And Fernández Domínguez, Amilcar Orlián (2022), “*Speculative Bubble Tendencies İn Time Series Of Bitcoin Market Prices*”, *Cuadernos De Economía*, S.41(86), Ss.159-183.
- Diba, Behzad And Grossman, Herschel (1988), “*Explosive Rational Bubbles İn Stock Prices?*”, *The American Economic Review*, S.78(3), Ss.520-530.
- Fendı, Usama Adnan, Maalı, Bassam Mohammad And Atmeh, Muhannad Ahamd (2023), “*Rational Speculative Bubbles İn The Stock Market - The Case Of Amman Stock Exchang*”, *Afro-Asian Journal Of Finance And Accounting*, S.13(1), Ss.68-84.
- Guo, M., Wang, S., & Wei, Y. (2025). Bubbles İn Nft Markets: Correlated With Cryptocurrencies Or Sentiment Indexes?. *Applied Economics Letters*, 32(4), 491-497.
- Kartal, Gökhan (2022), “*Konut Piyasasında Çoklu Balon Oluşumu: Türkiye Geneli Ve Tr71 Bölgesinden Ampirik Deliller*”, *Ömer Halisdemir Üniversitesi İktisadi Ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, S.15(2), Ss.343-360.
- Kılıç, Yusuf (2020), “*Finansal Piyasalarda Balon Varlığının Test Edilmesi: Brics-T Ülkeleri Örneği*”, *Bankacılık Ve Sermaye Piyasası Araştırmaları Dergisi*, S.4(9), Ss.11-22.

- Korkmaz, Özge, Erer, Deniz And Erer, Elif (2016), “*Alternatif Yatırım Araçlarında Ortaya Çıkan Balonlar Türkiye Hisse Senedi Piyasasını Etkiliyor Mu? Bist 100 Üzerine Bir Uygulama*”, Bddk Bankacılık Ve Finansal Piyasalar Dergisi, S.10(2), Ss.29-61.
- L1, Yan, Chevallier, Julien, Wei, Yigang And L1, Jing (2020), “*Identifying Price Bubbles In The Us, European And Asian Natural Gas Market: Evidence From A Gsadf Test Approach*”, Energy Economics, S.87(3), Ss.(104740).
- L1, Y., Wang, Z., Wang, H. Et Al. Identifying Price Bubble Periods İn The Bitcoin Market-Based On Gsadf Model. *Qual Quant* **55**, 1829–1844 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11135-020-01077-4>
- L1, Zheng Zheng, Xiao, Yidong And Su, Chi-Wei (2021), “*Does Covid-19 Drive Stock Price Bubbles İn Medical Mask?*”, Asian Economics Letters, S.2(4), Ss.1-6.
- Liaqat, Ayesha, Nazır, Mian Sajid And Ahmad, Iftikhar (2019), “*Identification Of Multiple Stock Bubbles İn An Emerging Market: Application Of Gsadf Approach*”, Econ Change Restruct, S.52, Ss.301-326.
- Marcu, Mihaela Roxana (2021), “*The Impact Of The Covid-19 Pandemic On The Banking Sector*”, Management Dynamics İn The Knowledge Economy, S.9(2/32), Ss.205-223.
- Ogunnusi, Mercy, Mansur, Hamma-Adama, Huda, Salman And Tahar, Kouider (2020), “*Covid-19 Pandemic: The Effects And Prospects İn The Construction Industry*”, International Journal Of Real Estate Studies, S.14(2), Ss.120-128.
- Phillips, Peter, Shi, Shuping And Yu, Jun (2015), “*Testing For Multiple Bubbles: Historical Episodes Of Exuberance And Collapse İn The S&P 500*”, International Economic Review, S.56(4), Ss.1043-1078.
- Sharma, Shahil And Escobarı, Diego (2018), “*Identifying Price Bubble Periods İn The Energy Sector*”, Energy Economics, S.69, Ss.418-429.
- Temir, Cem (2020), “*Covid-19’un Sermaye Piyasaları Üzerine Etkisi*”, İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Girişimcilik Dergisi, S.4(7), Ss.50-66.
- Torun Kayabaşı, Ehlinaz (2020), “*Covid-19’un Tarımsal Üretime Etkisi*”, Avrasya Sosyal Ve Ekonomi Araştırmaları Dergisi, S.7(5), Ss.38-45.
- Türkoğlu, Diler (2021), “*Covid-19 Salgınının Risk Bileşenleri Üzerindeki Etkisi: Katılım Model Portföy Endeksi*”, Uluslararası Muhasebe Ve Finans Araştırmaları Dergisi, S.3(2), Ss.1-25.
- Ulusoy, T. & Civek, F. (2020). “*Covid-19 Öncesi Ve Sonrası Dönem İçin Enflasyon Ve Faiz Değerlendirmesi: Abd-Türkiye-Çin*”, International Social Mentality and Researcher Thinkers Journal, (Issn:2630-631X) 6(39): 2626-2636
- Wang, Mei-Chih, Chang, Tsangyao And Min, Jennifer (2022a), “*Revisit Stock Price Bubbles İn The Covid-19 Period: Further Evidence From Taiwan’s And Mainland China’s Tourism Industries*”, Tourism Economics, S.28(4), Ss.951-960.
- Wang, Yizhi, Horky, Florian, Baals, Lennart J., Lucey, Brian M. And Vigne, Samuel A. (2022b), “*Bubbles All The Way Down? Detecting And Date-Stamping Bubble Behaviours İn Nft And Defi Markets*”, Journal Of Chinese Economic And Business Studies, S.20(4), Ss.415-436.
- Wang, Zuyi And Kim, Man-Keun (2022), “*Price Bubbles İn Oil & Gas Markets And Their Transfe*”, Resources Policy, S.79, Ss.(103059).